

ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF MARKETING PROGRAMS IN LEADING GLOBAL COMPANIES

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According to global practices, U.S. companies were among the first to prioritize the use of marketing programs. In this context, it is important to highlight the statement made by Jack Welch, the CEO of General Electric (GE), a company considered a "driver" of the U.S. industrial sector. Welch stated: "It is necessary to incorporate innovations into the company's operations by anticipating changes in market demands; otherwise, the company's activities will face a crisis." This statement indicates the direct link between a company's operational efficiency and the use of marketing programs. Additionally, it is well documented that during Jack Welch's tenure (1981-2001), GE's economic efficiency improved dramatically compared to previous leadership. As a result, when Welch retired in 2001, he was awarded a retirement package worth \$417 million.

This highlights the crucial role marketing programs play in enhancing the effectiveness and economic performance of leading companies like GE.

During Jack Welch's tenure as CEO of General Electric (GE), the company underwent significant structural changes in its management practices. Welch prioritized ensuring that every management decision was closely tied to the company's marketing programs. This integration of marketing into management allowed GE to maintain a strong alignment between its production activities and consumer needs.

According to research conducted by U.S. economists Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller, GE's use of marketing programs played a crucial role in fostering the connection between production and consumers. As a result, the company achieved impressive economic outcomes, demonstrating that marketing programs were a key driver of its financial success.

In general, General Electric (GE) is a multinational company founded on April 15, 1892, and has been a leader in the U.S. industrial sector for over 130 years. Throughout its long history, GE has played a significant role in promoting the innovative development of industrial sectors in the United States. The company holds a prominent position not only in the U.S. but also in the global economic system, being one of the most diversified multinational corporations. Today, GE has more than 150 subsidiaries operating in various countries around the world, reinforcing its global influence.

The use of marketing programs in General Electric's (GE) operations has shown characteristics that are later observed in other major companies such as **Sears, Levi's, General Motors, Kodak, Xerox, Microsoft, Walmart, Intel, and Nike**. These companies adopted similar marketing practices, emphasizing the integration of marketing strategies into their overall business operations. This approach helped align production with consumer demand, improving economic performance and fostering long-term growth, much like it did for GE.

In this context, it is worth noting the statement by Jim Koch, founder of **Boston Beer Company**, regarding the development of his company's operations: "We continuously seek revolutionary approaches to transform beer enthusiasts' perceptions of this frothy beverage through market research, and we develop and implement these innovations into our business operations." This highlights Koch's focus on using innovative marketing strategies, driven by market research, to reshape customer perceptions and incorporate new ideas into the company's activities. This approach to innovation has been central to Boston Beer Company's success and growth in the competitive beverage industry.

Based on the insights shared by Jim Koch, founder of the **Boston Beer Company**, a leading producer of beverages in the U.S. food industry, it can be concluded that in a market economy, the key factor for the development of any company's operations is directly linked to the effective use of marketing programs. This includes organizing business activities, making informed management

decisions, and achieving strategic development goals. The success of a company is closely tied to how effectively it integrates marketing programs into its overall business strategy, ensuring alignment with market demands and long-term growth objectives.

At the same time, the development of the use of marketing programs in companies' operations has led to significant changes in management practices. Specifically, marketing programs have driven the development of **quality management** within companies. As noted earlier, marketing strategies have encouraged companies to focus on improving product quality to meet consumer expectations more effectively.

According to global practice, the use of marketing programs has evolved and improved in line with industrial revolutions. Many scientific studies confirm that these revolutions have influenced how companies implement marketing strategies. Therefore, it is essential to analyze the characteristics of the industrial revolutions that have shaped these practices globally, as they provide valuable insights into the continuous advancement and refinement of marketing program usage.

Analysis shows that leading global companies prioritize the use of marketing programs aimed at specific target consumers by properly segmenting the market. By implementing these targeted marketing programs, companies focus on increasing the volume of market turnover for their goods and services. Additionally, when entering new markets, companies make extensive use of **brand marketing programs**. These strategies help businesses introduce their products to new audiences, establish strong brand recognition, and increase their overall market presence, ultimately driving growth and success in both existing and emerging markets.

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